

The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law & Economics

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Introduction

The vast majority of articles and books that have been written about economics -- nearly all -- take a utilitarian perspective. Economists are known as utilitarians, and it might even be said that someone who discusses an economic question from a nonutilitarian perspective is not making an economic argument. I am not saying that such a statement is true, but only that it could and has been said. Nearly all the literature in the interdisciplinary area of law and economics is written from a utilitarian perspective.

In the area of tax policy, utilitarians take the position that a policy is good if it reduces the amount of distortion in the system,² or if it increases efficiency. The same view is taken of any other economic policy. Utilitarians take the position that if free trade is a good policy, it is good because the vast majority benefits. Free trade gives consumers more choices. It gives them lower prices. It creates more jobs than it destroys. It is a positive-sum game. An underlying assumption of most utilitarian-based arguments is that governments have some inherent right to regulate capitalist acts between or among consenting adults.³

This paper looks at economic policy from a different perspective. While utilitarian approaches to economic policy have

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² Utilitarians measure the goodness or badness of a tax policy based on how close the policy comes to neutrality. A neutral tax is held to be the perfect tax.

³ Robert Nozick uses this terminology in *ANARCHY, STATE AND UTOPIA* (1974).

some value, and while utilitarian arguments often reach the correct conclusion, they do so for the wrong reason. For example, if utilitarians conclude that free and unrestricted trade is the best policy, they do so because free trade is a positive sum game. But the real reason why totally free and unrestricted trade is good is because it is the only trade policy that does not violate individual rights. The correct rule of thumb for determining whether a policy is good or bad should not be whether it is a positive-sum game, but rather whether the policy violates anyone's rights, properly defined.

Problems with Utilitarian Approaches to Economic Policy

There are several problems with taking a utilitarian approach to economic policy issues. The fatal flaw is that the utilitarian approach ignores property and contract rights. But there are other weaknesses as well.

One weakness with the utilitarian approach is that it is not possible to accurately measure gains and losses.⁴ So if the goal is to achieve the greatest good for the greatest number, one must work with estimates. Economics textbooks present their examples of the application of marginal utility theory in terms of units, which they call utils. Each util is assigned a numerical value. And with each additional purchase, the marginal utility declines.

For example, let's say that Jane is very hungry. She goes into a fast-food restaurant and orders a hamburger for \$1. Since she is very hungry, the value of the hamburger, to her, is 10 utils. And since \$1 is worth only 3 utils to her,⁵ her satisfaction is

⁴ For a detailed critique of this point, see MURRAY N. ROTHBARD, *MAN, ECONOMY, AND STATE* 260-68 (1970).

⁵ She places a value of 3 utils on one dollar, but other consumers may place different values on one dollar. A rich person may place a value of 0.005 utils on one dollar, whereas a poor person may assign a value of 20 utils to one dollar. And the number of utils' value for a dollar may change with the same individual. As the individual spends more dollars, thereby reducing the supply of dollars, the value of the next dollar -- the marginal dollar -- may change. So the value of a dollar to a particular individual can change. It is not necessarily constant. It should also be pointed out that a rich person does not necessarily derive fewer

increased by surrendering the \$1, worth 3 utils, for a hamburger that is worth 10 utils.⁶ She has gained to the extent of 7 utils. After finishing the first hamburger, she must decide whether consuming a second hamburger would increase her happiness. If she values the second hamburger at 6 utils and the next dollar in her purse at 3 utils, she will decide to purchase a second hamburger because doing so will increase her satisfaction. So she exchanges a dollar, worth 3 utils, for the second hamburger, worth 6 utils. After consuming the second hamburger, she must decide whether to buy a third hamburger. If the value of a third hamburger to her is only 2 utils, she will decide not to buy, since she is better off keeping her dollar, which is valued at 3 utils, rather than exchanging it for something that has a value to her of only 2 utils.

The problem inherent in using this approach is that utils are defined in terms of definite, measurable units, whereas choices are actually ranks. We can say that she prefers two hamburgers to \$2, but we cannot say that she gains 6 utils by making an exchange. Economics textbook writers use utils to illustrate how the marginal utility theory works. But utils actually do not exist.

Attempting to apply the marginal utility theory to international trade or any other economic policy presents some problems. For example, if a certain protectionist measure is applied to a particular product, we cannot determine by precise measurement whether the gains received by the domestic

utils of benefit from a dollar than does a poor person. This relationship is often assumed by economists (the graduated income tax is based on the validity of this assumption), but this assumption may be invalid.

⁶ It should be pointed out that these values are subjective. If the seller of hamburgers also valued \$1 at 3 utils and one hamburger at 10 utils, there would be no trade because the seller of hamburgers would be worse off if a trade transpired. The reason any trade takes place is because the buyer and seller place different values on the products or services they buy and sell. Both parties to a trade gain, in their own subjective judgment. The seller of hamburgers would rather have the \$1 than the hamburger and Jane would rather have the hamburger than the \$1.

producers exceed the losses incurred by domestic consumers. And it should also be pointed out that domestic producers and consumers are not the only ones affected by protectionist policies. Foreign producers, their employees, the companies that would otherwise transport the foreign product to the domestic market, the domestic import companies and their employees, and the businesses that would otherwise receive a portion of the import companies' employee salaries are also affected.

Let's say that a particular protectionist measure causes the price of the average shirt to be \$5 higher than would be the case under free trade. So millions of consumers have to pay an extra \$5 for a shirt, and domestic producers of shirts gain as a result. But they do not necessarily gain the same total amount as the loss that domestic consumers incur because some of the shirts consumers buy will be manufactured by foreign producers. So an induced cost increase also might benefit foreign producers (especially if the induced cost increase is the result of a quota rather than a tariff). The presence of a quota will reduce the number of shirts that a foreign producer can sell in the domestic market, but it will increase the unit price the foreign producer can charge, thus increasing foreign producer profit margins.

Fewer foreign shirts will be purchased as a result. Which means that the domestic import companies that would otherwise bring the shirts into the United States will lose business. So they will need fewer employees. And the money that these employees would otherwise earn cannot flow into the purchase of autos, clothing, and so forth because these employees do not have jobs as a result of the protectionist measure.

There is really no way to accurately measure the total gains and total losses that result from a particular protectionist measure because it is impossible to predict where the money will flow in the absence of protectionism. But it can be concluded, a priori, that total satisfaction will decrease if consumers have to settle for their second or third choice because some protectionist measure prevents them from buying their first choice.

Another way to look at the effect of a protectionist measure, in an attempt to determine whether the measure is good or bad, is to predict who would gain and who would lose if the particular policy were implemented. In the case of a protectionist measure on textiles, for example, millions of consumers stand to lose because they would have to pay higher prices.⁷ But a few domestic textile companies stand to gain by the passage of the measure. Based on this approach, it might be concluded that the protectionist measure is bad because many individuals (consumers) stand to lose something, whereas only a few stand to gain (domestic textile manufacturers). But this analysis is superficial because the unit gains and unit losses are not equal. The domestic textile producers stand to gain much if the measure becomes law, whereas the millions of consumers who lose something would only lose a little bit, perhaps \$5 per shirt.

Another fact to consider is that the textile manufacturers are highly organized special interests, whereas the majority, the consumers, are unorganized. It is in the textile manufacturers' best interest to expend large sums of money to lobby Congress to pass the piece of protectionist legislation. But it is rational behavior for the millions of unorganized consumers not to organize to petition Congress not to pass the bill. The cost of organizing, in terms of time, effort and money expended, is just not worth it. It is better to

⁷ Numerous studies have been made that attempt to measure the extent of consumer losses that result from protectionism in various industries. In textiles and apparel, some results have been as follows: GARY CLYDE HUFBAUER, DIANE T. BERLINER AND KIMBERLY ANN ELLIOTT, *TRADE PROTECTIONISM IN THE UNITED STATES: 31 CASE STUDIES* 146 (1986) (the induced price increase in textiles was 21%); WILLIAM R. CLINE, *THE FUTURE OF WORLD TRADE IN TEXTILES AND APPAREL* 15 (rev. ed. 1990) (the estimated price increase for textiles was 28%); HUFBAUER, BERLINER AND ELLIOTT 146 (1986) (39% price increase in apparel); Carl Hamilton, *An Assessment of Voluntary Restraints on Hong Kong Exports to Europe and the U.S.A.*, 53 *ECONOMICA* 339-50 (1986) (50% increase in apparel prices); Susan Hickok, *The Consumer Cost of Trade Restraints*, QTR. REV. (Fed. Res. Bank of NY), Summer, 1985, 1-12 (46% to 76% increase in apparel prices); CLINE 15 (1990) (53% increase in apparel prices).

pay an extra \$5 a shirt than to try to counterbalance the special interest that has the ear of the legislature.

This phenomenon is present regardless of which industry is involved. The steel industry, auto industry, farm lobby and every other producer of domestic goods stand to gain, in the short-run at least, if they can convince Congress to protect them from foreign competition. So it pays them to organize. And it is rational behavior for the consumers of these items not to organize because the cost of doing so exceeds the benefits to be gained by organizing.⁸ Thus, the special interests have a built-in advantage over consumers.

The Public Choice School of Economics has been discussing this point for several decades. Wherever the costs of lobbying are low and the potential benefits are high, special interests will run to government for protection or special favors. Public Choice economists call this phenomenon rent-seeking -- the seeking of special privileges or protection from government or getting others to pay for your benefits.⁹

⁸ There are some exceptions, of course. In some cases, one organized special interest lobbies Congress to pass a piece of protectionist legislation while another, opposing special interest lobbies Congress not to pass it. For example, in some instances, the steel industry's attempt to lobby Congress has been opposed by industry groups that use steel. And domestic auto producers that try to restrict foreign imports have been opposed by foreign car dealerships. So there is sometimes organized opposition, a countervailing power where special interests do battle with each other. For some case studies detailing specific instances where special interest groups have engaged in this kind of activity, *see* I.M. DESTLER AND JOHN S. ODELL, *ANTI-PROTECTION: CHANGING FORCES IN UNITED STATES TRADE POLITICS* (1987).

⁹ For more on the concept of rent-seeking, *see* *TOWARDS A THEORY OF A RENT-SEEKING SOCIETY* (James M. Buchanan, Robert Tollison and Gordon Tullock eds. 1980); *THE POLITICAL ECONOMY OF RENT-SEEKING* (Charles K. Rowley, Robert D. Tollison and Gordon Tullock eds. 1988) (Pages 217-37 apply the theory of rent-seeking to trade regulation); GORDON TULLOCK, *THE ECONOMICS OF SPECIAL PRIVILEGE AND RENT SEEKING* (1989); GORDON TULLOCK, *PRIVATE WANTS, PUBLIC MEANS: AN ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF THE DESIRABLE SCOPE OF GOVERNMENT* (1970; 1987).

Another basically utilitarian argument is the public policy or common good argument. If a policy of free trade is good, it is good because it is in the public interest or it is for the common good. The fatal flaw in this line of reasoning is that there is no such thing as "the public." The public is just a collective term to describe the general citizenry. The public does not eat, sleep and breathe. Only individuals do these things. Only individuals have interests. And in a pluralist society, these interests conflict.¹⁰ Auto manufacturers (their stockholders and employees, actually) have an interest in seeing protectionist legislation passed to protect them from foreign competition. And the millions of individuals who purchase autos have an interest in having low prices and a wide variety of choices. Foreign auto producers also have an interest in selling their products on the domestic market. While it might be concluded that the public interest is in free trade, this conclusion is reached on utilitarian grounds -- the consumers who stand to gain by free trade outnumber the auto company stockholders and employees who stand to gain by protectionism (the interests of the foreign auto producers, their stockholders and employees are usually ignored in arriving at this determination).

Ayn Rand has the following point to make about the concept of the public interest:

Since there is no such entity as "the public," since the public is merely a number of individuals, any claimed or implied conflict of "the public interest" with private interests means that the interests of some men are to be sacrificed to the interests and wishes of others. Since the concept is so conveniently undefinable, its use rests only on any given gang's ability to proclaim that "The public,

¹⁰ Michael Novak points this out in *FREE PERSONS AND THE COMMON GOOD* 19-22 (1989).

c'est moi" -- and to maintain the claim at the point of a gun.¹¹

Aside from this inherent weakness in the public interest argument is the fact that the argument is sometimes used to protect special interests at the expense of the general public. It has been argued that the passage of antimerger legislation is in the public interest, when in fact such legislation often serves to protect entrenched, inefficient management at the expense of shareholders, consumers and the general public.¹² The farm lobby argues that it is in the public interest to have a strong farm sector, so Congress passes legislation to subsidize the farm industry and protect it from foreign competition at the expense of the general public.¹³ Industry leaders whose companies are losing market share from foreign or domestic competition petition Congress to regulate their industry to prevent cutthroat competition, in the public interest.¹⁴ But the effect of such legislation is to keep prices abnormally high, compared to what they would be in a free market. Most antitrust actions are initiated not by government, but by competitors who see their market share eroded by more efficient competitors.¹⁵

¹¹ AYN RAND, *THE VIRTUE OF SELFISHNESS* 116 (1964); *see also* THE AYN RAND LEXICON: OBJECTIVISM FROM A TO Z 396 (H. Binswanger ed., 1986).

¹² For a discussion of this point, *see* Robert W. McGee, *Mergers and Acquisitions: An Economic and Legal Analysis*, 22 CREIGHTON L. REV. 665-93 (1988/89).

¹³ For more on this point, *see* JAMES BOVARD, *THE FARM FIASCO* (1989).

¹⁴ The Interstate Commerce Commission and numerous other government agencies were created to protect industry leaders from loss of market share to smaller, more competitive companies. For documentation of this point, *see* GABRIEL KOLKO, *RAILROADS AND REGULATION 1877-1916* (1965); GABRIEL KOLKO, *THE TRIUMPH OF CONSERVATISM* (1963).

¹⁵ D.T. ARMENTANO, *ANTITRUST AND MONOPOLY: ANATOMY OF A POLICY FAILURE* (1990); D.T. ARMENTANO, *ANTITRUST POLICY: THE CASE FOR REPEAL* (1986). For an in-depth discussion of how the antitrust laws have been used by rent-seekers to feather their own nests at the expense of the general public, *see* WILLIAM F. SHUGHART II, *ANTITRUST POLICY AND INTEREST-GROUP POLITICS* (1990).

Members of various professions and occupations such as doctors, lawyers, accountants, hair dressers, electricians, opticians, pharmacists, morticians, auto mechanics, speech therapists, tattoo artists, and so forth petition the legislature to pass licensure laws to protect the general public from quacks, when research shows that the loosening or repeal of such laws results in higher quality service at lower cost.¹⁶

Another, related argument is the balancing of interests argument, or the balancing of rights argument. This argument takes the position that the rights of some individuals or groups must be balanced against the rights of other individuals or groups. But this argument is just another variation of the basic utilitarian argument. It is grounded in positive rights theory, which is fatally flawed.¹⁷

The balancing of rights argument, when applied to trade theory, argues that the rights of foreign producers to sell their products on the domestic market must be balanced against the rights of domestic producers to be protected from dumping or unfair competition. There are several weaknesses with this line of reasoning. For one thing, the right of consumers to buy the products of their choice from the sellers of their choice is often ignored. But more importantly, this argument assumes that domestic producers have some right to sell their products even though consumers do not want to do business with them. Domestic producers do not have their rights violated when a

¹⁶ MILTON FRIEDMAN, *CAPITALISM & FREEDOM* 137-60 (1962); *OCCUPATIONAL LICENSURE AND REGULATION* (Simon Rottenberg ed. 1980); S. DAVID YOUNG, *THE RULE OF EXPERTS: OCCUPATIONAL LICENSING IN AMERICA* (1987); *OCCUPATIONAL REGULATION AND THE PUBLIC INTEREST* (Robert Albon and Greg Lindsay eds. 1984); S. GROSS, *OF FOXES AND HENHOUSES: LICENSING AND THE HEALTH PROFESSIONS* (1984).

¹⁷ The balancing of rights theory is often discussed in connection with the First Amendment. For a discussion on this point, see Ronald A. Cass, *The Perils of Positive Thinking: Constitutional Interpretation and Negative First Amendment Theory*, 34 U.C.L.A. L. REV. 1405 (1987).

foreign producer "dumps" products on the domestic market.¹⁸ Although they may be harmed by foreign dumping, their rights are not violated because they have no property rights in transactions that consumers do not want to enter into with them.

If a supermarket opens up across the street from a mom and pop grocery store, there is no doubt that the mom and pop store will be harmed by the competition. It may even be driven out of business. But it cannot be said that their rights are violated by having the supermarket set up shop across the street. The supermarket has every right to open a store across the street (not to mention the fact that consumers will benefit by lower prices and a larger selection) and mom and pop have no right to prevent consumers from taking their business across the street if they want to. Government has no right to prevent the supermarket from opening because there are no rights to "balance." Although the interests of mom and pop are diametrically opposed to the interests of the supermarket, government has no business balancing these interests in one direction or the other. The real issue is rights, not interests. When people speak about balancing "interests," what they really mean is balancing "rights." But in a negative rights regime,¹⁹ rights can never conflict. You have the right to property and so do I. You have the right not to be killed or confined and so do I. It is only in a positive rights regime that rights can conflict because the right of one individual or group must be sacrificed so that another individual or group can gain something. Thus, the balancing of interests argument suffers from several structural weaknesses.

¹⁸ Many foreign producers that are accused of dumping their products on the market are not really dumping, in the sense that they are not selling for less than the cost of production. And even if they are, so what? Consumers benefit by the practice. Foreign producers can also be found guilty of dumping if they sell their products for less than "fair value." But aside from the fact that "fair value" is a completely arbitrary concept, this practice also does not harm consumers. And it does not violate anyone's rights.

¹⁹ Negative and positive rights are discussed below.

The Rights Approach

A major problem with any utilitarian argument is that it is impossible to precisely measure the total gains and the total losses. So it is not possible to determine in many cases whether a particular policy results in the greatest good for the greatest number. But the fatal flaw in any utilitarian approach is that utilitarian approaches ignore individual rights. If the good outweighs the bad, a utilitarian would not be concerned that someone's rights have to be violated to implement the policy.

To illustrate this point, let's take an example. Let's say that John is, and always has been, a sex-craved maniac. He has just been released from prison after ten years of incarceration. During that time he has not had sex. And he is prowling the streets with the goal of making up for lost time. He comes upon a prostitute who is lying on the sidewalk in a drunken stupor. He drags her into an alley and rapes her. While he is ripping off her clothes, she protests by mumbling that he should stop. But she does not put up any resistance and actually falls asleep while he is committing the crime.

She has experienced almost no discomfort or disutility as a result of John's act. But John has experienced a great deal of pleasure. Has society benefited by the act? A utilitarian would conclude that it had. One person gained and one person lost as a result of the rape. So it appears to be a zero-sum game. But the person who gained, gained a great deal, whereas the person who lost, lost only a little. So the gains exceed the losses, even if John's utility gain and the prostitute's utility loss cannot be measured precisely, and the act can be declared to be good on that account.

The example is outrageous, but the thought process a utilitarian uses to arrive at a conclusion cannot be faulted on utilitarian grounds. The reader may be quick to point out that the prostitute's rights were violated in a very personal way by John's action. But rights violations are of no concern to a pure utilitarian theorist. All that matters to a utilitarian is whether the gains

exceed the losses. The idea that someone's rights might have to be violated to achieve the goal is not worthy of consideration.

But violating someone's rights is never necessary to achieve a worthy goal. If someone's rights must be violated to achieve a goal, the goal is not a worthy one in the first place. Utilitarian approaches all begin with the premise that the end justifies the means. Rights approaches begin with the premise that it is the process that is important, not the destination. A trade policy based on utilitarianism can have protectionist elements if it is determined that the gainers from the policy exceed the losers, or if it is determined that "society" benefits as a whole. Under a rights approach to trade policy, "society" is not even at issue. The issue is whether someone's rights, properly defined, are violated by the policy. If rights are violated, then the policy is a bad one. If no one's rights are violated, then the policy is not a bad one.²⁰

Which brings us to another important question: What exactly are rights, anyway? Philosophers over the centuries have viewed rights from two different and diametrically opposed perspectives. Negative rights include the rights to life, liberty and property. Stated in negative terms, they would be the right not to be killed, the right not to be involuntarily confined, and the right not to have your property taken from you without your consent. Negative rights are inherent. They are not rights that are granted by government. They are rights that come before government. Governments are instituted to protect these rights.

Positive rights advocates view rights from a different perspective. Examples of positive rights include the right to medical care, the right to subsidized rent, and so forth. Positive rights are rights that are granted by government. They are not inherent. And they are rights that are gained at someone else's expense.

²⁰ Rights-based approaches do not get into morality issues. Ticket scalping, polygamy, prostitution, drug legalization, etc., may or may not be immoral, but whether they are or not does not affect the rights-based analysis. According to rights theory, a practice should be allowed as long as it does not violate anyone's negative rights to property, contract, association, etc.

Under a positive rights regime, the rights of some must be sacrificed so that others may have rights. In the case of medical care, for example, those who claim a right to medical care gain this right at the expense of others, who must provide it. Free medical care does not mean that medical care is costless. Someone (the taxpayer) has to pay. But it is free to the recipient because the recipient incurs no out of pocket costs.

Rent control laws also work in this manner. If the law prevents a landlord from charging \$800 a month (the market rate) for an apartment, the difference between the actual rent and the market price for the apartment is, in effect, a forcible transfer of property from the landlord to the tenant. If the maximum rent that can legally be charged is \$500 and the rent that could be charged in a free market is \$800, then the landlord is, in effect, having \$300 of his property confiscated each month and having it transferred to the tenant. The tenant's "right" to affordable housing comes at the expense of the landlord. If the tenant lives in a government subsidized housing project, the result is the same, except that it is the taxpayer rather than the landlord who has to pay for the tenant's right to affordable housing.

Losses always exceed gains under a positive rights regime if for no other reason than the fact that there are transaction costs. The landlord will not voluntarily write out a \$300 check to the tenant each month. There has to be an enforcement authority around the corner that is ready to enforce the law if the landlord does not want to comply. And an army of bureaucrats has to be retained to see that the various redistributive laws are properly administered and enforced. So it cannot be said that a positive rights regime is a zero-sum game, because the losses do not exactly offset the gains. The landlord loses \$300 a month and the tenant gains \$300 a month, but the cost of maintaining the enforcement authority must also be counted, which leads to a negative-sum result. Economists call this net loss a deadweight loss.

But whether this policy or that is a zero-sum game, a negative-sum game or a positive-sum game is really beside the point. Discussions about whether a policy is a negative-sum or

positive-sum game are utilitarian because the object is to determine whether the gains exceed the losses. In a rights regime, gains and losses are irrelevant. All that matters is whether rights are violated -- in the negative sense of the term.

Summary and Conclusion

The vast majority of economic arguments are fatally flawed because they begin (at best) from a utilitarian premise. If a trade agreement is indeed intended to be pro-consumer rather than protectionist,²¹ advocates take the position that the trade policy should be implemented because it benefits the majority, or that it benefits consumers, or that it is in the public interest. But a proper position to take is that a trade policy should be implemented or adopted if it does not violate anyone's rights. The public interest, public policy or other majoritarian arguments are totally beside the point and do not address the real issue. Whether some policy benefits the majority is irrelevant, not to mention not always easy to determine.

Arguments about the gains and losses involved in adopting this policy or that are off the mark and only lead the debaters astray from the real issue. Whether a policy should be adopted should be determined solely on the basis of whether anyone's rights are violated. If a policy would violate anyone's contract, property or other negative right, the policy should not be adopted. And if an existing policy violates anyone's contract, property or other negative right, it should be abolished immediately. The proper function of government is to protect life, liberty, property and contract rights and to otherwise leave people alone to seek their happiness in their own way. These are the only functions that a government can rightly perform in a pluralist society where individuals have different interests and goals. Governments that prevent consenting adults from entering into voluntary exchange are going beyond their legitimate scope.

²¹ It cannot be said that all trade agreements fit this description. Some are intended to be protectionist.